

COMPOSITE MATERIALS SUSTAINABILITY – WHERE ARE WE TODAY AND WHERE DO WE NEED TO GO

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ABSTRACT

When engineers and composite material practitioners talk about sustainability and composites, they could be talking about any one of the several aspects of this idea. But the basic question is how do we make our composite structures sustainable, and what do we do with them when they come to the end of their current usefulness. This is the over-riding concern for the industry today, especially as our most prevalent composite structures come to the end of their useful life. The most visible example of this is the current mountain of used wind turbine blades that are piling up in Sweetwater, Texas. But this is not the only problem that the industry faces, it is just the most visible one.

There are many challenges that engineers face when it comes to what to do about sustainability and composites, not the least of which is how sustainability is defined. Is it just being able to recycle these materials and keep them from landfills, or potentially does it mean that the industry needs to wean itself off of the use of petroleum feedstocks for the building blocks for advanced composites of tomorrow.

On the recycling front, several techniques for reuse have emerged in the last decade, from grinding up used composites and using the ground up material as reinforcement for things like concrete or sheet molding compound, to pyrolyzing the resin and keeping the fiber, to complete separation of the matrix from the fibers through thermal or chemical means and reusing both in new composites. This last challenge is of course the most technically difficult to actually achieve, since great pains were taken to make the fibers adhere to the resins in the first place. It also has been perceived as cost prohibitive.

On the inherently sustainable front, there is also a move toward using bio-based precursors for both fiber and resin, and using resin chemistries that are inherently recyclable. This trend is expanding rather rapidly but has yet to reach a tipping point where bio-based or plant-based precursors for composites become the standard.

Clearly there is more work to be done. What follows provides an up to date assessment of where all of the composite materials sustainability efforts are and offers a guide or roadmap to where each part of the industry needs to go and what needs to be done to achieve true sustainability.

To achieve this eventual goal all sectors of the industry need to be involved. This includes at least the manufacturers (growers?) of the precursors, the resin and fiber manufacturers, the manufacturers and purveyors of the different product forms that need to be made available, the fabricators and composites manufacturers, the end users, and the recycling / reuse community.

To achieve true sustainability in the industry will cost money and take time and effort on the part of every sector of the industry. In addition, there is inherent risk associated with upending business models that have worked for the last few decades which are not going to be workable in the future. The challenge is transforming the business without going out of business. This paper provides a roadmap to accomplish just that.

1 INTRODUCTION

Several schools of thought have emerged in this field in the last decade, and there is considerable ongoing work in the industry to achieve sustainability. While the technologies to recycle composites have been demonstrated in the laboratory and even at small scale, the work ongoing now is in scaling up these newly developed methods to recycle large composite parts that have come to the end of their life. This work is driven both by the wind energy industry as large composite wind turbine blades come to the end of their lives, and the marine industry in recycling of end of life boat hulls. Most of this work is for fiberglass composites, since fiberglass is the highest tonnage waste problem that the industry faces. These developments are also mostly in the EU because of the new environmental laws that require that boat manufacturers not only bake in the cost of recycling their end of life boat hulls but also accept them

for recycling when they come to end of life,. It is also because of the early adoption of offshore wind in the North Sea where wind turbines need to be repowered regularly because of the extraordinarily harsh environment they must withstand.

There is, of course, more to the story than just recycling of existing parts. Other practitioners and composites designers view sustainability from different angles than just how to keep wind turbine blades and old boat hulls from being put in a landfill. There is now, however, a movement in the industry to develop and use design and fabrication methods that take into account how the part is going to be recycled and its constituents reused at the end of use of the part that they are designing. Essentially what all of this means is how do we close the design-fabrication-use-recycle-reuse circle in order to avoid having to make new fibers and resin systems every time we want to make a composite part or structure.

Figure 1 illustrates this idea of creating a circular economy for composite materials to achieve real sustainability of these materials.

Figure 1: Linear vs Circular Economy (© Government of the Netherlands)

This figure was chosen to present here because it demonstrates what is meant by the creation of a circular economy for composite materials as compared and contrasted with the current linear economy where end of life composites are mostly put in landfills. This is of course where the industry is tending and needs to go to make these materials sustainable.

There is also a movement in the industry to formulate resins that can be more easily reverted into their initial liquid state through either chemical or thermal means so that they can be more readily separated from the fibers. There are even means of thermally removing the resin from the fibers without damaging the fibers and without burning up the resins so that both recycled materials can then be reused.

Sustainability in composites also means moving away from the use of petroleum as a feedstock for both fibers and resins and moving to plant-based fiber and resin precursors. To that end, plant fibers like flax have begun to be used effectively in a number of composite structures. Research is also going on to develop composite resins from wood product waste that behave like epoxies. The paper industry uses the cellulose from wood and essentially throws away the lignin that binds the cellulose fibers together. Use of this discarded lignin as a precursor to an epoxy resin is a very active field of technology development.

Finally, there is a large movement to enable design of composite parts in a manner that takes into account the entire life cycle of the material from design to material selection to fabrication to use and eventual recycling and reuse once the part has ended its usefulness. This is called Design for Sustainability, which is a very important initiative that has been started in Europe by the European Composites Industry Association – EuCIA.

This paper presents not only the challenges that engineers, chemists, and other scientists face in creating a model of sustainability for composites that is cost effective and accomplishes the goals of sustainability, but also provides a roadmap to sustainability as well as a snapshot of where the industry is today on that road to true sustainability. This includes first a look at the challenges that the industry

faces in moving from the current linear business model to a circular business model for these materials, then provides a presentation of the state of the art in this field of endeavor and who is working on what part of the problem. The story that unfolds here then continues by providing a roadmap for engineers and practitioners in composite material design, fabrication, use, and recycling/reuse. Finally what is presented is a look at the state of the art in composites sustainability and a discussion of not only where we are on that road but also what it is going to take in terms of technology development, capital expense, and time.

2 CHALLENGES FACED BY THE INDUSTRY

The major challenge that the composites industry faces in the very near future stems fundamentally from the properties of composite materials in that their major benefit is also their Achilles heel. Composites provide an infinite number of different ways that you can combine a fiber or other reinforcement and a matrix material – whether that be a plastic, metal, or even ceramic – to make a material that is greater than the sum of its parts so to speak. This wonderful benefit, when the composite comes to the end of its useful life, makes the material very difficult to separate into its constituent parts and reuse those parts. This means that there is a large amount of this waste that is no longer allowed to be landfilled in most countries. This is especially true of the wind turbine industry where it is believed that by 2034 there will be on the order of 200,000 tons of blade waste produced per year [2]. And, of course, since wind turbines are getting much larger in terms of blade length, there is a move to migrate to an all carbon/epoxy blade design from the current carbon fiber/epoxy spar with a glass/epoxy skin to minimize swing weight of the propeller blades. This will only make the recycling problem more challenging.

2.1 Wind Turbine Industry Challenges

The fundamental challenge facing this industry is realizing a positive cost/benefit in real dollars from recycling used fiberglass wind turbine blades when the market for the recycled materials has historically been nearly non-existent. This has been true for decades which is why so many wind turbine blades are rotting in landfills all over the developed world. There are news stories about this problem, and some infamous pictures from places like Sweetwater Texas where there is an enormous pile of used wind turbine blades stacked up and just sitting in the Texas sun that have been there for more than a decade without a single blade being moved to a recycling center.

Figure 2: Used Wind Turbine Blades in Sweetwater, Texas (photo by Eli Rosen, Yucca Films)

There are similar piles of these blades in the UK and in Northern Europe where they used to commonly be landfilled. This is changing, however because the EU and the UK have both banned the

landfilling of wind turbine blades, so there are significant efforts ongoing to deal with this problem in a responsible way.

Currently the process for recycling these blades when they come to their end of use is to chop up the blade into smaller pieces and use these pieces in a discontinuously reinforced composite. This has its own drawbacks because of the loss of the stiffness and strength of the original continuous fiber composite. Some authors and practitioners have suggested that pyrolyzing the blades to remove the resin and leave just the remaining fiber is one way to preserve at least the continuous fiber. This process in itself poses many challenges. First, the blades that are coming into the waste stream now, as mentioned above, are a mix of carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy materials. Each of these components needs to be separated from the others and treated in a different manner, especially if pyrolysis is the method used to remove the resin from the fibers. And pyrolysis is not effective for fiberglass composites because the temperatures involved merely melt the glass and all you get is a pile of useless trash.

The major challenges with this method are both that pyrolysis does not preserve the resin (a petroleum based product) for reuse in another application, and also pyrolysis itself is not an eco-friendly process. The byproducts of epoxy resin pyrolysis are toxic and need to be extracted from the exhaust stream of the pyrolysis oven. The carbon from the original resin also is typically vented to the atmosphere and therefore adds to the carbon burden in our upper atmosphere. For these reasons, pyrolysis, while it may be a good place to start with recycling large end of life composite parts, is not the eventual answer to development of a sustainable, circular economy for the composite materials industry.

2.2 Recreational Marine Industry

The recreational marine industry has a very similar problem in recycling of the fiberglass boat hulls as exists in the wind turbine industry. Fiberglass boat hulls have an average life of about 30 years, with some lasting more than 50 years, but most, especially those exposed to seawater, have a shorter life span. And, like wind turbine blades, the fiberglass structures are very large, complex, and have all sorts of things attached to them that are not fiberglass.

The National Marine Manufacturers Association estimates that in the US some 200,000 boats reach the end of their useful life each year [2]. In the EU that number is more like 80,000 boats. If you consider that each boat hull is about a ton to a few tens of tons, this makes the problem nearly as difficult as the wind turbine blade waste problem. In addition to that, wind turbine blades are usually not widely disbursed whereas boat hulls are everywhere, so a centralized recycling strategy will not work.

2.3 Aging Aircraft

The Boeing 787 Dreamliner was introduced in 2012, and the Airbus A350 was introduced in 2013. These two commercial aircraft now have been manufactured at a high enough rate to meet demand, so there are several hundred of each in service today. These are the two best examples of a primarily composite large transport aircraft. As of February 2023, there had been 1041 Boeing 787's put into service and 524 Airbus A350's. Even though the pandemic has reduced both aircraft production rates substantially (14 787's per month in 2020 and 10 A350's per month in 2019) at their current production rates (9 per month for both Boeing and Airbus) [3], more than 2000 of these composite aircraft are going to have to be recycled and reused in the next 20-30 years.

To date there has only been a modicum of research and development work done to effectively recycle the composite material portions of these aircraft. While there has been considerable research into this topic, which is gaining some traction both here in the U.S. and in Europe, development of all of the technologies required to effectively recycle and reuse the composite parts of these large transport aircraft have yet to be developed.

2.4 Automotive Industry

In the last decade or so a considerable number of composite material parts have been integrated into new cars and trucks, both light duty and also heavier over-the-road trucks. Ford for instance makes some of their light duty truck driveshafts out of composites. And increasingly composites are being used for things like leaf springs, trunk liners, and some body parts. With the coming of electrification of the mass auto market, things like battery cases are also being made out of composites [4].

Composites have been used in mass market automobiles and light trucks since 1953 with the introduction of the Corvette. Since then, every Corvette has had a fiberglass body. Since the advent of the Corvette fiberglass body, several composite components have been introduced, until finally composites entered the mainstream of the auto industry in 1984 with the Pontiac Fiero and continued in 1990 with the introduction of the Saturn [5]. Since that time with the perfection not only of the injection molding and vacuum assisted resin transfer molding as well as thermoset and thermoplastic based sheet molding compounds, nearly all trunk liners, fender well liners, interior door panels, and even some exterior fenders, door panels, and hoods of standard high production rate automobiles have been made using composite materials. Since these materials are a mix of thermoset and thermoplastic resin composites, they pose different challenges than the primarily glass and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites used in the wind turbine and air transport sectors.

It has been said that as soon as carbon fiber gets down to on the order of \$5 a pound, the auto industry will stop using steel. While this is a very good thing for the environment, since lighter weight autos burn less fuel, when these composite parts come to the end of their useful life in 20-30 years, there will be a need for a well-developed and cost effective means of recycling these materials that allows the reuse of the original constituents of the composite.

2.5 Other Composites

There are a number of other smaller industries that albeit do not create a large tonnage in each, are large enough that in total they are also becoming a problem. Most of these are smaller parts and widely distributed enough that only local recycling centers will receive them. A good example is sporting goods – golf club shafts, tennis rackets, skis, football and hockey helmets, paddleboards and paddles, surf boards, canoes and kayaks, and more.

Unfortunately most of these smaller composite goods are such that new “better” models are released on a regular basis, and the old model either gets put in the closet, or worse, sent to the dump. This means that when a golfer replaces their clubs with the “new and improved” carbon fiber shaft clubs, the old ones are thrown out. Unfortunately most of these items are too small and are too widely dispersed for there to be a national or even regional effort to recycle them. This means that most are merely buried in landfills rather than being recycled.

3 STATE OF THE ART IN COMPOSITES RECYCLING AND REUSE

The current state of the art in composite recycling is that by and large these materials are not being recycled to any great extent. There have been some efforts in reuse of these materials, specifically used wind turbine blades, but these are mostly demonstration projects and there are not enough applications of the used blades to make this a long term solution.

There is, however, some light at the end of this long tunnel. The European Union has been leading the way in this regard, primarily because of the environmental sensitivity of the European public and the support of National leadership in the EU. Quite unlike in the US, there has been a concerted effort ongoing for some time to achieve sustainability in all European activities, including and most importantly the industrial sector. This culminated in the European Green Deal, which was adopted in the EU in 2019, and has formed the backbone of the European environmental regulatory environment. Efforts in the composites industry had been ongoing for some time, based on the “Waste Framework Directive” which was adopted in 1991 and has spawned a number of companies in the composites recycling business.

Another European directive, called the “Extended Producer Responsibility” where producers of composite structures are responsible for their end of life management. This rule has been applied fairly recently in both the recreational marine and wind turbine or renewable energy sectors.

Along with these regulations, also quite unlike in the US, the EU is providing support in terms of direct funding and support for collaborations between companies and universities at no cost to companies that develop composite recycling technologies that have the potential to scale up to a size appropriate for the sector that the company wants to work in.

3.1 Fiberglass – Mostly Wind Turbine Blades and Boat Hulls

One Italian company – Korec in Bientina, Italy (Tuscany) – is working with Owens Corning here in the US to scale up their fiberglass recycling technology. Owens Corning has taken it upon themselves to reduce their carbon footprint by 50% and using 100% renewable energy for processing by 2030. This is a fairly ambitious goal.

Korec's patented process (US Patent Number 10,308,784) is a thermo-chemical process where they use CO₂ in the absence of Oxygen to dissolve the resin at high temperature. When they extract the hot gas from the chamber, all of the resin has been depolymerized and is contained in the gas, which is then condensed out of the gas and reprocessed.

Figure 3. Korec Process (with permission from Korec)

Another company in the French speaking part of Switzerland – Composite Recycling – has also developed a process along the same lines as Korec primarily for end of life wind turbine blades. They use another proprietary pyrolysis-like process that they call thermolysis, in the absence of oxygen to depolymerize the resin from waste glass fiber composite materials and recover most of the resin in the form of what they call “thermolysis oil”. This company is working with an engineering firm in Sweden, Fiberloop, that developed this process and is building their industrial scale machines. The process is able to separate the resin from the fibers, and recovers not only polyester resins, but also epoxies, albeit at a slightly higher temperature but still not as high as traditional pyrolysis. Fiberloop is in the business of designing and assembling machines for clients with specific needs like Composite Recycling. Their business relationship has Fiberloop building each machine to Composite Recycling’s specifications based on each client’s needs, and Composite Recycling operates the machine at the site where the recyclable material exists. In addition, Composite Recycling has done all of the testing required to get both their reclaimed glass fiber and their thermolysis oil certified as ready to use for the wind turbine industry as well, and they have already established supply chains for selling their product into the marketplace.

The one unique thing that Composite Recycling has done is to bring their fiberglass recycling machine to the site of the recyclable composite materials – as in at a wind turbine blade dump – rather than having used wind turbine blades shipped to a central recycling facility. They have been able to fit their entire glass fiber composite recycling process and equipment along with all of the chemistry required in a 40’ ISO container. And they have recently joined a consortium led by Beneteau to enable the recycling of end of life boat hulls. This consortium includes Beneteau, Composite Recycling, specialty resin company Arkema, waste management company Veolia, Owens Corning, and textile specialists Chomarar. All of these companies are leaders in their sector of their businesses, especially in Europe.

Figure 4. Rendering of Composite Recycling Containerized Recycling Machine (Courtesy Composite Recycling)

3.2 Carbon Fiber – Mostly End of Life Fighter Aircraft

Quite a bit less work has been done in recycling of carbon fiber composites primarily because they are a much lower tonnage problem than fiberglass. Carbon fiber composites have not been in general use until fairly recently except for the high performance aerospace structures required for both spacecraft and modern fighter aircraft. Of the space applications of carbon fiber composites, there has been zero effort to reclaim or recycle them for obvious reasons, but for aging fighter aircraft this is not the case. There are now several early generation fighter aircraft, both in the US and the EU that have been retired because their airframes have been used up. There has therefore not been the need nor the demand to recycle carbon fiber composites to any large extent.

That is, however changing and changing rather rapidly. To wit, there are a few efforts that have been successful, and a few companies have sprung up to begin commercialization of their recycled carbon fiber products. The initial recycling efforts for these materials used to involve a pyrolysis step where the resin is effectively burned off of the carbon fiber, leaving the fiber relatively intact while exhausting the combustion products from the resin pyrolysis into the atmosphere.

In the last several years, a few newer and less carbon intensive technologies have arisen that are in the process of being scaled up to the level where they could be called industrial scale. One company in South Carolina, Carbon Conversions, which got its start from an SBIR grant developed a process in collaboration with MIT that can reclaim nearly virgin carbon fiber from nearly any source of end of life carbon fiber composites. They fairly recently got funding from Boeing and demonstrated the reclamation of carbon fiber from an F-18 and used that fiber to create a Corvette body.

Another company in the Denver area, Vartega, has taken on the process of recycling uncured carbon fiber prepreg scrap into usable carbon fiber. In a similar development, a much larger company based in Paris, Fairmat, has also developed a process for recycling scrap carbon fiber prepreg at a much larger scale. They recently announced an agreement with Hexcel in Salt Lake City to recycle all of the scrap uncured carbon fiber prepreg from Hexcel's manufacturing facility. This is an extension of an ongoing relationship between Hexcel and Fairmat that started in Europe, but this is a fairly large undertaking because the Salt Lake Hexcel facility is the largest of all of the Hexcel manufacturing facilities. In another similar development, Toray's Pacific Northwest facility in Tacoma, Washington which services mostly Boeing, has signed an MOU with Elevated Materials in Gardena, CA to do much the same thing as Vartega and Fairmat.

While none of these is an actual recycling method for end of life carbon fiber composites that retains both the fiber and the resin, there have been demonstrations of this technology at least in the EU. The Fiberloop / Composite Recycling partnership has demonstrated that their thermolysis process works well on typical aerospace epoxy resins in high performance carbon fiber composites. Apparently what they do is to process the epoxy-based composites at a somewhat higher temperature than the typical polyester resins in most fiberglass composites.

4 INHERENTLY RECYCLABLE COMPOSITE RESINS

There are several approaches to making inherently recyclable composites, some based just on the resins, some focusing only on the fiber, and some based on both the resin and the fiber. The approach to making recyclable resins falls into two categories, those using petroleum feedstocks and those using plant-based oils or plant-based compounds as precursors. So, let's start there and then move on to sustainable composites in general

4.1 Petroleum-Based Recyclable Resins

In the petroleum based world, typically what this means is that the chemistry of the epoxy precursors is modified in such a way that the cross-linking that makes the epoxy a solid can be unlinked through the use of special catalysts and/or specific organic acids. Quite a bit of this chemistry was developed some time ago, but it has not found broad use in the past because there was not a perceived need to make these materials inherently recyclable. An additional hurdle has also been that the inherently recyclable epoxies typically do not possess the same high level of mechanical properties (strength, stiffness) as traditional epoxies. There have been some recent developments in this area but none have made it out of the laboratory.

4.2 Plant-Based Recyclable Resins

Plant-based recyclable resins are something of a mixed bag. While there are a few partially bio-based resins and some mixes of these that are inherently recyclable, there are only a handful of fully plant-based and inherently recyclable resin systems.

One good example of these is a fairly recent development by NREL in Golder, Colorado. Researchers at NREL created an entirely plant based resin system they call PECAN [6] (PolyEster Covalent Adaptable Networks) that is essentially a high performance epoxidized polyester-type resin that has roughly equivalent mechanical and processing properties as typical aerospace epoxies. NREL demonstrated the efficacy of this resin system by building and testing a 9 meter long wind turbine blade. The effort at NREL was in the Wind Energy Technology Center there and was focused on sustainability in the wind energy sector, which is why the first full demonstration of this new resin system was to make a commercially viable wind turbine blade.

Another good example is from a Taiwanese company named Swancor. They have developed a paired system they call EzCiclo and CleaVER. EzCiclo is a fully recyclable thermosetting epoxy resin system that has properties equivalent to aerospace grade epoxies. This system was developed for the growing wind energy industry in Asia to provide a sustainable alternative to the standard petroleum-based and non-recyclable epoxies used for wind turbine blades. While Swancor does not disclose the chemistry of their EzCiclo resin and CleaVER chemical treatment, they have demonstrated this technology successfully for several industries.

5 PLANT-BASED SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES

In order for the industry to become truly sustainable, and to become more than just carbon neutral but become a carbon sink, the industry understands that at some point the precursors for making fibers and resins must come from plants, and the process energy to make the fibers and resins must come from renewable sources. Fortunately there is considerable ongoing work in this area with some actual commercialization beginning to happen.

5.1 Natural Fibers

The most common natural fiber that has been adopted by the composites industry is flax fiber. This is the fiber of the linen textile industry, and the two areas that produce the most of it are France and North America, with France being the largest of the two. There are established supply chains for flax fiber and flax fiber textiles, and these fibers have been adopted by a number of high volume industries. In the automotive industry, flax fiber is used for interior door panels not only because it is inexpensive and easy to work with, but also because flax fiber composites have both heat and sound insulating properties that neither glass nor carbon fibers possess. Flax fiber also has a better strength to weight ratio than other industrial fibers, so the auto industry has used it also to save weight primarily in

not a naturally occurring compound, synthesis of it from plant-based precursors is typically more expensive than sourcing it from the petrochemical industry.

Bisphenol-F which is a naturally occurring compound found in prepared mustard and the roots or rhizomes of plants used in traditional Chinese medicine, has found use in the marine industry and consumer goods for a number of years. These are the “BPA free” plastics and resins that are suitable for use for food preparation as well as other consumer goods. Epoxies made using bisphenol-F are roughly equivalent in stiffness to their BPA cousins, with slightly lower strength and also slightly lower viscosity, making them good candidates for things like VARTM. This is why they have found use in the pleasure marine industry since quite a few production boat hulls are made using this vacuum assisted resin infusion method.

In the Netherlands, Frog Biosystems B.V. has produced an epoxy resin from rapeseed oils that they blend with traditional petroleum based epoxy to make what they call Fairpoxy. This resin has a 29% plant-based epoxy content and is equivalent to modern aerospace epoxies.

In the U.S., Entropy Resins which was recently acquired by the Gudgeon Brothers of West System fame has also developed a plant-based epoxy that they also mix with petroleum based epoxies to various extents to make a variety of different resin systems.

Finally, one fairly recently concluded project in the EU – the ECOxy Project – was a consortium of 13 partners focused on the R&D necessary to convert all sorts of plant precursors into useful epoxy resins, along with several other composites sustainability goals. While that Project concluded in late 2020, one of their partners – Specific Polymers SP – wrote an article on the Project site that has a wonderful graphic about making resin precursors from wood dust, algae, and vegetable oils. This graphic is actually from Specific Polymers because they are commercializing the results of the ECOxy project.

Figure 6: Specific Polymers Bisphenol-Free Plant Based Epoxy (courtesy Specific Polymers)

Specific Polymers now has a complete line of these bio-based epoxy resins that they have for sale on the open market. They are marketing them as bisphenol-A free epoxies based on forest products waste (wood dust), algae, and agricultural waste in the form of plant oils. Two products that they have on the

market are DGEVA – a vanillin-based epoxy resin, and PHTE (Phloroglucinol Triglycidyl Ether).

In addition to the creation of the bisphenol backbone for epoxies, another molecule also needs to be added in order to put epoxide groups on the bisphenol backbone to make the epoxy resin itself. The molecule that is the most prevalent in this chemistry is epichlorohydrin. Epichlorohydrin is traditionally made using propene from petroleum based sources, but it can also be readily made from glycerol, and is actually somewhat easier to make from glycerol than it is to make from propene. And, since glycerol is a byproduct of the production of biodiesel, it is also readily available.

There are several companies in the business of making epichlorohydrin from bio-based glycerol. Sicomin sells their products under the trade name of GreenPoxy, Advanced Chemical and Advanced Biochemical in Thailand also sells a plant-based epichlorohydrin as does Syensqo, a Louisiana company named Louisiana Chemical Equipment Company, a UK based company called TechnipFMC with main office in Houston, as well as a plant in India that also makes plant-based epichlorohydrin. All of these companies sell their products mainly into the traditional plastics manufacturing business and have very nearly taken over the epichlorohydrin manufacturing business from the petrochemical industry. This is one of the real success stories in bio-based plastics precursors.

The bottom line here is that the future of plant or bio-based resins is rather bright, and companies on nearly every continent in the developed world are moving rapidly away from petroleum feedstocks. So, while there is still quite a bit of work to do here, at least this part of the business is trending in the right direction.

6 ROADMAP TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE FOR COMPOSITES

While what is presented in this paper paints a fairly optimistic picture of the state of the art in recyclability, lowering the carbon footprint of composites and also the transition to an entirely sustainable plant-based future for composites, there is still considerable work to be done. There are developments ongoing on several fronts, from the development of technologies that can separate traditional resins from their fibers (thermolysis and solvolysis), to inherently recyclable resin systems that can be easily taken apart at the end of their useful life, to plant-based precursors for both fibers and resins.

What remains to be done is for the industry to transform itself from its current non-sustainable large carbon footprint to a more sustainable business model that can actually become a carbon sink, all while staying in business and being in business making these materials into the far future. There is a road to get to this end result, and it will require considerable capital investment and work in scaling up all of these technologies while still providing the current products that are needed today. That is the challenge, and there is a way to get there.

Here are some recommendations to get everyone started:

- **RECOMMENDATION 1 – Create Sustainable Strategies** – Find or create sustainable strategies for your specific products and base the strategies on things that you can accomplish both in the short term and the long term. In other words, make an actionable plan for the future with measurable milestones and stretch goals to get to a completely sustainable model for the business that you are in.
- **RECOMMENDATION 2 – Partner with Startups** – Larger companies have a tendency to have bureaucratic inertia that does not permit them to make drastic changes to their business model rapidly or easily. They might also not have the right technical resources and creative personnel required to make these changes. Startups that have good ideas and that are run by technical expert entrepreneurs make good partnerships with larger companies and can have a very positive effect on the outcome of the implementation of these technologies.
- **RECOMMENDATION 3 – Be Willing to Accept Risk** – This is rather difficult for large more traditional companies, but to make the transformation and potentially to begin to lead rather than follow, it is necessary to accept the risk that you won't get it right the first time. This is difficult for traditional companies like those in heavily regulated industries like the petrochemical industry, so if necessary, form a "skunk works" of your own and establish separate management of that so that the larger company does not have to take all of the risk.
- **RECOMMENDATION 4 – Work With Others and With National Societies and Not-For-**

Profits – There is a wealth of talent available to materials and manufacturing businesses if they join and participate in societies like SAMPE, ASME, ACS, and on boards of composites manufacturing associations like ACMA and EUCIA.

- **RECOMMENDATION 5 – Seek Government funding for Transformative Technologies** – There are multiple opportunities with the Federal Government in a number of agencies and Departments (Agriculture, Commerce, Defense, etc.) to get funding for transformative technologies. And, while it used to be that the Government wanted to own the intellectual property resulting from Government-Industry collaborations, such is not necessarily the case anymore. Starting with the Baye-Dole act in 1980 (43), companies and universities who develop technology in partnership with the federal government and with federal funding are no longer required to relinquish the patent rights to that technology to the government.
- **FINAL RECOMMENDATION / STRATEGIC IMPERATIVE – Don't go Out of Business While Changing the Business** – this is probably the most important concept and/or mantra to take into this arena. No matter what, it is imperative that companies making this transition not lose focus on their current business while in the process of transforming their business.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has hopefully provided not only the state of the art in composite materials sustainability, but also the status of some ongoing efforts that show promise in reducing or eliminating the carbon footprint of the industry. In addition, a roadmap with realistic recommendations has been presented here to enable the industry to follow a path to sustainability that will allow them to stay in business making a profit while fundamentally transforming their business.

It is clear that this transformation will take time, money, and the concerted efforts of everyone in the business in order to be successful. What is clear is that every sector of this industry and every aspect of how we make, use, and deal with end of life composites needs to be part of this overall roadmap. True circularity is quite literally philosophical in that what comes from the earth must at some point be sent back to the earth in such a way that the earth can make more of the stuff that needs to come from the earth again. And while this may seem naïve at first or even impossible to some, it is actually the definition of a circular economy.

Of course, this road is still long and full of potential potholes and dead ends. In other words, it is going to take time, a lot of very hard work, an ability to accept and embrace failures along the way, and an enormous investment on the part of the industry to make this come to pass.

It is also going to take enlightened and capable leadership in all of the companies that are in this industry. It is the leaders of this industry that are going to be the drivers of change in each of their companies that will lead us to success and a sustainable, circular economy as the future of this industry. These leaders must be politically savvy, willing to take on calculated risk, and motivated by an understanding that their long term success depends on the decisions they make now and the path that they lead their companies down. Those are the leaders and the companies that will survive and prosper in a newly transformed and circular composites industry.

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